

Laser powder bed fusion of nano-CaB₆ decorated 2024 aluminum alloy

Philipp Mair^{a,*}, Valerie Sue Goettgens^a, Tobias Rainer^a, Nikolaus Weinberger^b,
Ilse Letofsky-Papst^c, Stefan Mitsche^c, Gerhard Leichtfried^a

^a Faculty of Engineering Sciences, University of Innsbruck, Department of Mechatronics, Materials Science, Technikerstrasse 13, 6020 Innsbruck, Austria

^b Faculty of Engineering Sciences, University of Innsbruck, Department of Structural Engineering and Material Sciences, Material Technology, Technikerstrasse 13, 6020 Innsbruck, Austria

^c Institute for Electron Microscopy and Nanoanalysis and Center for Electron Microscopy, Graz University of Technology, NAWI Graz, Steyrergasse 17, 8010 Graz, Austria

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ABSTRACT

The 2024 aluminum alloy (Al-Cu-Mg) is widely used in aerospace; however, due to its solidification-cracking tendency, its processability using laser powder bed fusion (LPBF) remains a critical issue. The addition of 2 wt% CaB₆ nanoparticles induces a columnar-to-equiaxed transition (CET), resulting in an immediate improvement in LPBF processability. High-density (>99.5%) and crack-free specimens, with a homogeneous equiaxed microstructure and without preferred grain orientation, were obtained. The small average α -Al grain size of $0.91 \pm 0.32 \mu\text{m}$ is attributed to the similar lattice constants of Al and CaB₆ facilitating Al nucleation on CaB₆ nanoparticles, resulting in a highly coherent Al/CaB₆ interface. CaB₆ nanoparticles act as heterogeneous nucleus and exert a pinning force on the grain boundaries, which reduces grain coarsening. The as-built specimens exhibit both high-yield strength ($348 \pm 16 \text{ MPa}$) and high-tensile strength ($391 \pm 22 \text{ MPa}$), combined with a high total elongation at break ($12.6 \pm 0.6\%$). The macro hardness amounts to $132 \pm 4 \text{ HV}_5$.

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1. Introduction

The 2024 aluminum alloy is a high-strength, heat-treatable wrought alloy with copper (Cu), magnesium (Mg) and manganese (Mn) as the main alloying elements. Its high specific strength and fatigue resistance make it one of the most widely used metals in the aerospace, automotive and defense industries. With demand growing for complex-shaped parts, laser powder bed fusion (LPBF), the leading technology in additive manufacturing (AM) for metallic materials, offers new opportunities [1]. The unique property of layer wise powder fusion by a precise high-energy laser beam results in a solid component with a high degree of geometrical freedom. The highly localized heat source leads to fast cooling rates (thermal gradient $[G] \sim 10^3 - 10^6 \text{ K/s}$ [2]), resulting in a distinctive non-equilibrium microstructure. Although numerous alloys have been processed with LPBF, only a limited number (approximately 15 – 20) are commercially available and able to tolerate the special requirements of the LPBF process. The chemical composition of high-strength age-hardenable aluminum alloys (series 2xxx, 6xxx and 7xxx) makes

them unsuitable for the LPBF process [3]: they contain alloying elements which significantly increase the solidification temperature range of the alloy [3–5]. Consequently, these alloys tend to segregate low melting phases during epitaxial grain growth; typical for aluminum alloys that cannot be processed in the LPBF process [3]. Tensile deformation, caused by solidification shrinkage and thermal contraction, can be induced in the interdendritic semi-solid, resulting in solidification cracks extending over the entire length of the columnar grain [6–8].

The introduction of effective heterogeneous grain refiners has been shown to successfully reduce crack sensitivity of high-strength heat-treatable aluminum alloys [3,5,9–16]. Inoculants, either directly introduced [3,9–11] or formed in situ [5,12–16], that have the smallest possible lattice mismatch to the α -Al matrix can act as a nucleant and thus induce a transition from a columnar to an equiaxed microstructure. This increases the total area of the grain boundaries, per volume, reducing the thickness of the residual liquid film at the end of the solidification stage and inhibiting crack initiation and propagation.

The successful processing of the 2024 aluminum alloy was facilitated by Tan et al. [17] who investigated densification behavior and defect formation in a wide processing window; the results showed that when processing parameters were optimized, porosity

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: ph.mair@uibk.ac.at (P. Mair).

was < 1%, but cracks along columnar grains could not be eliminated. The addition of 0.7 wt% Ti nanoparticles, which form a high number of fine, dispersed, and fully coherent Al₃Ti intermetallic precipitates eliminated hot cracks and the columnar structure and refined the grains in the 2024 alloy [9].

Hexaborides, such as CeB₆ [18], LaB₆ [19–21], CaB₆ [22], SrB₆ [23] and NdB₆ [24], have the potential to be used as efficient grain refiners in aluminum alloys, due to their cubic crystal structure and similar lattice constants as aluminum solid solution (α -Al). Orientation relationships (ORs) have been identified for each of these, with coherent interfaces between the hexaborides and the α -Al. In this study, a composite powder, consisting of an aluminum alloy 2024 decorated with CaB₆ nanoparticles was fabricated (hereafter referred to as ND-2024; ND \triangleq nano-decorated). CaB₆ is a high-performance ceramic, which crystallizes in a cubic structure (CsCl-type) with a $Pm\bar{3}m$ space group. Its unit cell ($a = 4.145\text{\AA}$) exhibits only a small lattice parameter mismatch of +2.55% with the face-centered cubic (fcc) structure of aluminum ($a = 4.049\text{\AA}$) [25]. By comparing and systematically characterizing the microstructures of LPBF processed samples from undoped 2024 and LPBF ND-2024 specimens, the ability and efficiency of CaB₆ as a heterogeneous grain refiner for 2024 was investigated.

2. Materials and methods

The 2024 powder was produced by Toyo Aluminium K.K. (Japan), by inert gas (N₂) atomization. Its chemical composition was determined by inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES) using a Varian Vista MPX (Varian Inc., USA). The following values were measured (in wt%): Cu (4.40), Mg (1.70), Mn (0.60), Si (0.07), Fe (0.07), Cr (0.01), Zn (0.01) and Al (balance). According to the supplier (Jinzhou Haixin Metal, China), the CaB₆ powder (99.0% purity) consisted of nanoparticles with a mean particle size of 200 nm.

The decoration of the 2024 aluminum alloy powder with 2.0 wt% CaB₆ nanoparticles was carried out in the laboratory planetary mill (PM100, Retsch, Germany) for two hours under an argon (Ar) atmosphere. A rate of 150 rpm and a ball to powder weight ratio of 1:1 was applied. The following methods and equipment were used to characterize the properties of the starting powders and the decorated powder used for the LPBF process. The particle size distribution was measured using a Malvern Mastersizer 2000 (Malvern Panalytical Ltd., UK). The tap/bulk density was measured according to ISO 3923 standard. The powder flowability was characterized using the Hausner ratio, a ratio of tap density over the bulk density [26,27]. The laser reflectivity of the starting 2024 aluminum alloy powder (RAW-2024) and the decorated powder (ND-2024) was determined using diffuse reflectance UV-Vis spectroscopy (DRS). DRS was carried out in the 200–2000 nm wavelength range, using an Agilent Cary 5000 UV-Vis-NIR Spectrophotometer (Agilent, USA), equipped with an internal DRA-2500, PMT PbS detector. The powder morphology was investigated using an FEI Quanta 3D 200 (FEI, USA) scanning electron microscope (SEM).

After sieving (mesh size 63 μm), the LPBF experiments were conducted on the RAW-2024 and ND-2024 powders. A laboratory-scale AconityLAB machine (Aconity, Germany), equipped with a 1064 nm Nd:YAG fiber laser and substrate plate heating was used. Specimens were built onto a pure Al platform, preheated to 200 °C. During the LPBF process, high purity Ar gas ($\geq 99.99\%$) was fed into the building chamber with an outlet pressure of 50 mbar, thereby decreasing the O₂ content below 25 ppm. Stripe scanning strategy (stripe size: 10 mm) with zig-zag pattern and a scan direction rotation of 67° between consecutive layers was applied. The parameter optimization was carried out for both RAW-2024 and ND-2024 powders using laser powers, P_L , between 200 W and 300 W and scan speeds, v_s , between 600 mm/s and 1200 mm/s. The layer

thickness, t_L , was fixed at 30 μm and the hatch distance, d_H , at 100 μm . These values correspond to an applied volume energy density (E_v) of 56–167 J/mm³, calculated from the following equation:

$$E_v = \frac{P_L}{v_s \times t_L \times d_H} \left(\frac{\text{J}}{\text{mm}^3} \right)$$

Cube-shaped specimens (13 × 13 × 13 mm) were built for microstructural characterization. The density of the cube-shaped specimens was measured according to Archimedes' principle. The calculation of the relative density was based on a theoretical density of 2.79 g/cm³ for the RAW-2024 and 2.78 g/cm³ for the ND-2024 powder.

Based on the preliminary test results, the following optimized building parameters were applied to produce the samples for further characterization of both materials: $P_L = 200\text{ W}$; $v_s = 1000\text{ mm/s}$; $d_H = 100\text{ }\mu\text{m}$; $t_L = 30\text{ }\mu\text{m}$.

Near-contour flat tensile test specimens were built for mechanical characterization of the ND-2024 material. The flat tensile test specimens were built in the testing direction, perpendicular to the building direction and with the flat side parallel to the substrate plate. Samples were separated from the substrate plate using mechanical milling. The near-contour tensile test specimens were milled to the desired final geometry according to ISO 6892: E 3 × 3 × 16.95.

Phase analysis of the feedstock powders and the as-built components were accomplished through X-ray diffraction (XRD) using an Empyrean Analytical (Malvern Panalytical Ltd., UK) in a Bragg Brentano configuration, with Cu K α radiation between 10° and 80°. Cube-shaped as-built specimens were non-destructively characterized through high-resolution 3D-imaging, using X-ray microscopy (XRM; Zeiss Xradia 520 Versa, Germany) to visualize porosity and cracks. A 4x objective lens (voxel size: 3 μm) and scanning energy parameters of 140 kV/10 W were used. The reconstruction of the 2D scans was performed using Zeiss XM Reconstructor software. Image analyses were performed with Zeiss XM3DViewer. Grain morphology and crystallographic orientation along the building direction (XZ or YZ plane) within the as-built components were investigated using an electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD) system mounted on a Zeiss Ultra 55 plus SEM (Carl Zeiss AG, Germany). The scan step size used for the EBSD maps was dependent on the image section: for overview scans with an image length of 500 μm , the scan step size was set to 500 nm; for detail images with an image length of 100 μm , 100 nm was set. Kernel average misorientation (KAM) maps were generated from the EBSD data of both alloys to identify local misorientation between grains. A JSM-7610F Schottky field emission SEM (Joel Ltd, Japan) fitted with an energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) system (EDAX, Ametek, USA) was used to analyze the fracture surface. For nano-scale characterization, specimens were prepared with argon ion milling, under cryo-conditions using a PIPS II System (Gatan Inc, USA). A probe corrected FEI Titan 3 G2 60–300 high-resolution scanning transmission electron microscope (STEM) was used to characterize the ND-2024 LPBF samples in as-built condition.

Tensile tests of as-built ND-2024 specimens were performed on an Autograph AG-X (Shimadzu, Japan) 10 kN machine at 20 °C. The strain rate for determining yield strength was kept at 0.00025/s, according to DIN EN ISO 6892-1:2017-02, then switched to 0.0166/s. The tensile tests were carried out with six samples. The Vickers hardness of RAW-2024 and ND-2024 specimens in as-built condition was measured using an EMCO Test M1C010 (Austria) at a load of 49.03325 N. Six indents were performed in each of three different samples. For tensile strength and hardness, mean values and standard deviations were calculated.

Table 1
Powder properties.

Material	D10 (μm)	D50 (μm)	D90 (μm)	Bulk density (g/cm^3)	Tap density (g/cm^3)	Hausner ratio; Flow description	Laser reflectivity (%)
RAW-2024	21.5	37.8	66.6	1.30 ± 0.04	1.53 ± 0.03	1.18; Good	47.3
ND-2024	19.8	36.0	65.0	1.31 ± 0.08	1.47 ± 0.02	1.12; Good	35.2

Fig. 1. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) images showing the powder morphology of (a) RAW-2024 powder; (b) CaB_6 powder; (c) RAW-2024 powder at higher magnification; (d) ND-2024 powder at higher magnification; (e) the laser reflectivity of RAW-2024 powder and ND-2024 powder; (f) particle size distribution of RAW-2024 powder.

3. Results

The physical properties of the RAW-2024 and the ND-2024 powders used in this study are listed in Table 1.

SEM images show the morphology of these powders (Fig. 1). According to the classification given by German [28], the RAW-2024 powder is largely spherical-rounded with some of the particles having a ligamental shape (Fig. 1a). The CaB_6 nanoparticles have a polygonal morphology and form agglomerations (Fig. 1b). Fig. 1c shows the smooth surface of an untreated RAW-2024 powder particle. Fig. 1d shows an ND-2024 powder particle that has retained its original morphology, despite the ball milling treatment and has a homogeneously decorated surface of CaB_6 nanoparticles. As shown in Fig. 1e, the laser reflectivity of the decorated ND-2024 powder, at a laser wavelength of 1064 nm is 35.2%, 12.1% lower than that of the RAW-2024 powder (47.3%). The particle size distributions for the RAW-2024 powder are given in Fig. 1f.

The results of the LPBF parameter analysis reveal the relationship between the relative density of LPBF specimens and the P_L and v_s used in LPBF, at constant t_L (30 μm) and d_H (100 μm) (Fig. 2). When processing the RAW-2024 powder with E_v increasing from 56 J/mm^3 to 167 J/mm^3 , the typical behavior of LPBF-processed materials is observed: with increasing E_v , relative density increases slightly, reaching a maximum of 98.3% then decreasing slightly when E_v increases further. In comparison, LPBF samples of ND-2024 alloy are almost fully dense. The highest relative density of $99.8 \pm 0.1\%$ was achieved at $E_v \sim 67 \text{ J}/\text{mm}^3$, which corresponds to the following parameters: $P_L = 200 \text{ W}$; $v_s = 1000 \text{ mm/s}$; $t_L = 30 \mu\text{m}$; $d_H = 100 \mu\text{m}$. All components for the subsequent investigation of the microstructure and mechanical properties were built with these parameters.

Fig. 2. Three-dimensional contour map showing the relative density of laser powder bed fusion (LPBF) samples in relation to the applied scanning speed (mm/s) and laser power (W), at a constant hatch distance of 100 μm and a layer thickness of 30 μm .

The phase analysis of powders and cross-sections of LPBF specimens, with the polished surface parallel to the building direction is illustrated in Fig. 3. All XRD patterns show with (111), (200), (220), and (311) the main crystallographic orientations of the face-centered cubic (fcc) α -Al phase. However, the RAW-2024 specimen exhibits a higher intensity for the (200) orientation and a smaller peak for the (111) orientation than the ND-2024 specimen. This indicates the

Fig. 3. X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns from RAW-2024 powder, ND-2024 powder and laser powder bed fusion (LPBF) as-built specimens: (a) the complete XRD pattern from 10° to 80° ; and (b) magnified areas of the pattern, representing low intensity phases.

presence of a texture in the RAW-2024 LPBF specimen, typical of Al-based materials that show planar solidification when processed with LPBF [29,30]. Besides α -Al as the main phase, Al_2Cu , Al_2CuMg and Al_3Mg_2 intermetallic phases are identified in minor quantities in all patterns. Compared to the starting powder, the peak intensity of these phases for the LPBF specimens is much smaller, because of the different cooling rates of LPBF ($\sim 10^3$ – 10^6 K/s [2]) and powder gas atomization ($\sim 10^2$ – 10^4 K/s [31]): a higher cooling rate leads to an increase in alloying elements (Cu, Mg) being metastable frozen in the α -Al solid solution. For the ND-2024 LPBF specimen, a low-intensity peak is observed because of the CaB_6 phase.

The results of the non-destructive examination by XRM of RAW-2024 and ND-2024 cube-shaped LPBF specimens are shown in Fig. 4. The as-built RAW-2024 specimen shows a 3D crack network (Fig. 4a). The main propagation of cracks is parallel to the building direction (z-axis). Along with a high incidence of cracks, a high degree of porosity is identified, with two different pore types observed: large irregular voids aligned parallel to the substrate plate and filled with partially melted, or non-melted powder particles and unfilled cavities. Fig. 4b shows that the addition of 2.0 wt% CaB_6 leads to a near-fully dense and crack-free specimen.

The EBSD inverse pole figure (IPF) maps show the crystallographic orientation of the α -Al grains, in a cross-section parallel to the building direction of both alloys in the as-built condition (Fig. 5).

The RAW-2024 specimen has a predominantly elongated columnar grain structure, with a grain width of 5–30 μm and a grain length of 80–150 μm (Fig. 5a and b). Its corresponding IPF and pole figure (PF) (Fig. 5h) indicate $\langle 001 \rangle$ fiber-texture parallel to the building direction. Solidification cracks, which are intergranular and extend over the entire length of the columnar grain, are also apparent. In contrast, an equiaxed, crack-free microstructure, with an average grain size of $0.91 \pm 0.32 \mu\text{m}$ is identified for the ND-2024 alloy (Fig. 5c). The IPF colors are randomly distributed, which indicates a texture-less alloy (Fig. 5c). The KAM distribution maps of both alloys are shown in Fig. 5d, e and f. Misorientation values in the vicinity of grain boundaries are $\sim 2^\circ$, whereas inside the grain they are $\sim 0^\circ$. Higher KAM values and accumulations of kernels (pixels) with high KAM values are located near the solidification cracks of the RAW-2024 alloy.

In order to uncover the crack surface and to enable the investigation of a solidification crack from the RAW-2024 sample by SEM, a cube-shaped specimen was subjected to tensile loading in the direction perpendicular to the building direction. Fig. 6a illustrates the surface of the intergranular solidification crack. Evaluation of the crack surface at higher magnification (Fig. 6b) shows localized fine cracks extending perpendicular to the building direction.

Figs. 7–9 show the transmission electron microscope (TEM) images of the as-built ND-2024 alloy. Fig. 7a presents a high-angle

Fig. 4. X-ray microscopy (XRM) images of (a) RAW-2024; and (b) ND-2024 laser powder bed fusion (LPBF) specimens in as-built condition.

Fig. 5. Electron backscatter diffraction inverse pole figure (EBSD-IPF) grain orientation maps in building direction of the as-built specimens of (a) RAW-2024; (b) RAW-2024 with higher magnification; and (c) ND-2024. The IPF color code for the EBSD-IPF orientation maps is shown in the lower right corner. The calculated {001}, {111} and {110} pole figures and the {001}, {101}, {111} IPFs of the RAW-2024 and ND-2024 specimens are shown in (h) and (i), respectively. The corresponding color scale in (g) indicates the relative intensity of the diffraction peaks. EBSD kernel average misorientation (KAM) maps of (d) RAW-2024, (e) RAW-2024 with higher magnification and (f) ND-2024 were retrieved from the EBSD-IPF orientation maps in (a), (b) and (c). The color scale, representing the misorientation angle values in degrees, is illustrated at the lower right corner (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article).

annular dark-field (HAADF)-STEM overview micrograph and Fig. 7b the corresponding EDX elemental maps of Al, Cu, Mg, Mn, Ca, B, Fe and O. At the grain boundaries there are Cu enrichments and, to a lesser extent Mg, Fe, and very small amounts of Mn. In accordance with the XRD pattern, the Cu-rich phase is Al_2Cu and Al_2CuMg . Cube-shaped particles, with dimensions between 50 nm and 250 nm are located partially within the α -Al grains and partially at the grain boundaries. The EDX maps in Fig. 7b illustrate that the nanoparticles consist of Ca and B. Two local quantitative EDX analyses (Table 2) of cube-shaped nanoparticles in Fig. 7 (marked with a yellow cursor) prove that it is CaB_6 . The CaB_6 nanoparticles were not observed within each α -Al grain, attributed to its 3D spread, depicted in a 2D image in only one sectional plane. To further investigate the grain refining mechanism of Al using CaB_6 nanoparticles, several high-resolution STEM images were taken from the interface between α -Al

and the CaB_6 nanoparticles. The ORs between the two crystals were determined. The annular dark-field (ADF)-STEM and HAADF-STEM images of two CaB_6 nanoparticles within an α -Al grain in Fig. 8a, b, e, and f provide an overview; the FEI-HAADF images (Fig. 8c and g), with corresponding fast Fourier transforms (FFTs), show the interface between α -Al and CaB_6 . The combined FFTs are illustrated in Fig. 8d and h. Both the α -Al matrix and the CaB_6 nanoparticle in Fig. 8a and e show parallel crystallographic axes oriented in the [0 0 1] and [1 0 1] direction, respectively. This indicates a highly coherent interface. On the CaB_6 nanoparticle surface, Al-Cu-Mg precipitates were frequently detected (Fig. 9). Next to these Al-Cu-Mg precipitates, small spherical particles enriched with O, Al, and Mg also formed. It can be assumed that these are oxide particles.

Table 3 summarizes the average hardness values for the as-built RAW-2024 and as-built ND-2024 materials, as well as yield strength,

Fig. 6. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) images showing the solidification crack surface of a RAW-2024 specimen at (a) lower magnification; and (b) higher magnification.

ultimate tensile strength, and total elongation at fracture for the ND-2024 material in as-built condition. As the RAW-2024 specimen had cracks, no tensile specimens were made from this material. A typical tensile stress-strain curve of the ND-2024 material in the as-built condition is shown in Fig. 10. The alloy exhibits a pronounced yield strength, followed by plastic deformation with little strengthening, before fracture at low necking occurred. Within the range of uniform plastic strain, a serrated and uneven deformation behavior is observed, which can be explained by the Portevin-Le Chatelier (PLC) effect [32]. The yield strength amounts to 348 MPa, the ultimate tensile strength to 391 MPa and a total elongation at fracture to 12.6%. The hardness of as-built ND-2024 is 132 ± 4 HV₅, double that of RAW-2024 (66 ± 6 HV₅). The hard CaB₆ ceramic nanoparticles and the high density contribute significantly to improving the macrohardness.

4. Discussion

The addition of 2 wt% CaB₆ nanoparticles to 2024 high-strength aluminum alloy enables its crack-free and pore-free processability. The LPBF processability of a powder depends, not only on its chemical composition, but also on various physical parameters, such as its size distribution, morphology, bulk density and laser reflectivity [33]. Despite the ball milling process, the composite powder retains its original morphology, and flowability and bulk density was not

adversely affected, thus ensuring a homogeneous spread of each powder layer. The high reflectivity of aluminum for laser radiation in the infrared range makes controlled melting difficult [34,35]. The improvement in laser absorptivity of CaB₆ decorated 2024 powder, at a laser wavelength of 1064 nm, reduces the difficulty of processing using LPBF. In addition to the high laser absorptivity of non-oxide ceramics [36], the increased surface roughness of CaB₆ decorated powder also could have a significant impact, due to multiple reflections in the powder bed [37–40].

The high-strength wrought 2024 aluminum alloy was designed based on conventional processing techniques and its chemical composition is not optimized for the high cooling speeds of the LPBF process. The poor processability is evidenced by the results of the detailed parameter analysis: no pore- and crack-free specimens could be generated from the RAW-2024 powder. The XRM analysis of the RAW-2024 specimen shows a high number of visible pores. Pore formation is due to two main factors: (1) low viscosity melt of the RAW-2024 material and (2) inadequate liquid feeding upon solidification. In terms of the first factor, an increased flow induced by Marangoni convection [41,42] and recoil pressure results in the ejection of a significant amount of molten droplets from the melting pool [43]. The impact of liquid spatters in the surrounding powder bed causes powder deposition defects. A rough underlying surface, with local powder accumulations and powder depletions are

Fig. 7. (a) High-angle annular dark-field scanning transmission electron microscope (HAADF-STEM) image of α -Al grains with cuboidal CaB₆ nanoparticles; (b) corresponding energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) maps for Al, Cu, Mg, Mn, Ca, B, Fe, and O. White and red arrows denote the CaB₆ nanoparticles inside the α -Al grains and at the grain boundaries, respectively (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article).

Fig. 8. (a) and (e) annular dark-field scanning transmission electron microscope (ADF-STEM) images of CaB_6 nanoparticles within an α -Al grain; (b) and (f) high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF)-STEM images of the same area as shown in (a) and (e); (c) and (g) HAADF-STEM images showing the area marked in (b) and (f) with rectangles at higher magnification: the z-contrast is evident, with the bright area being the α -Al matrix and the dark area representing the CaB_6 nanoparticles. The insets in (c) and (g) show the fast fourier transforms (FFTs) from α -Al and CaB_6 ; (d) and (h) show the combined FFTs. The α -Al matrix and the CaB_6 nanoparticle in (a) are oriented in $[0\ 0\ 1]$ direction. The α -Al matrix and the CaB_6 nanoparticle in (e) are oriented in $[1\ 0\ 1]$ direction.

formed, leading to lack-of-fusion pores aligned parallel to the substrate plate [43]. Additionally, unfilled cavities are formed by the strong melt flow of the low viscosity liquid metal within the melting pool [44]. Regarding the second factor, it is known that pore formation occurs during dendritic solidification in the mushy zone: this is the semi-solid zone with a large solid fraction, where coherency bridging between dendrites can be observed and, consequently, inadequate interdendritic feeding occur, resulting in pores and solidification cracks.

Large columnar grains, parallel to the building direction, dominate the microstructure of the RAW-2024 sample. This is expected as the localized energy source from the LPBF process leads to high values of the temperature gradient (G) (K/s) / growth rate (R) (m/s) [45]. As a result of the very high G ($\sim 10^3$ – 10^6 K/s [2]), undercooling at the solid/liquid (S/L) interface is not sufficient for heterogeneous nucleation and planar solidification is promoted, causing epitaxial

growth over several layers. The formation of columnar grains is accompanied by susceptibility to solidification cracks. These cracks, along columnar grain boundaries, are typical for conventional high strength aluminum alloys processed through LPBF. The alloying elements in 2024 aluminum alloy, in particular Cu, cause a wide

Table 2

Local quantitative energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) point analyses of the points marked with a yellow cursor in Fig. 7a.

Element	Atomic fraction (%)
Ca	8 ± 1
B	61 ± 5
Ca	10 ± 1
B	74 ± 5

Fig. 9. High-angle annular dark-field scanning transmission electron microscope (HAADF-STEM) image of (a) CaB_6 nanoparticle; (b) corresponding energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) maps for Al, Cu, Mg, Ca, B, and O.

Table 3
Mechanical properties of the RAW-2024 and ND-2024 alloys processed by laser powder bed fusion.

Material	Hardness (HV ₅)	Yield strength (MPa)	Ultimate tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at fracture (%)
as-built RAW-2024	66 ± 6	–	–	–
as-built ND-2024	132 ± 4	348 ± 16 MPa	391 ± 22 MPa	12.6 ± 0.6%

solidification range of 135 °C ($T_{\text{solidus}} = 503$ °C, $T_{\text{liquidus}} = 638$ °C [46]), promoting intergranular segregation of solutes during solidification. In the final stage of solidification, the residual melt, consisting of eutectic α -Al and Al_2Cu , is located within the long interdendritic channels and is subjected to high stresses caused by solidification shrinkage and thermal contraction during cooling. Solidification cracks occur along the grain boundaries. The remaining eutectic liquid, consisting of α -Al and Al_2Cu , solidifies at the solidification crack surface under high strain concentrations, resulting in locally occurring near-surface cracks, whose location corresponds to the increased KAM values ($> 2^\circ$).

The addition of 2 wt% CaB_6 nanoparticles to 2024 aluminum alloy greatly increases the density and, therefore, the processability. Despite a moderate CaB_6 melting point of 2235 °C [22], which is exceeded in certain zones of the melting pool during LPBF of aluminum alloys [47], decomposition of CaB_6 nanoparticles into Ca and B can be excluded, since no Al-Ca and Al-B phases were detected. The resulting increased viscosity of the ND-2024 melt dampens Marangoni-driven flow and reduces the spatter formation responsible for increased porosity [41,42]. As well as reduced porosity, crack formation is also prevented: the equiaxed microstructure is directly related to crack elimination. According to Martin et al. [3], equiaxed grains are easier to rotate and deform during solidification compared to columnar grains, so the resulting stresses are relieved more effectively. Furthermore, the transition from columnar to equiaxed grains considerably increases the total area of grain boundaries per volume, resulting in a significant reduction in the thickness of the residual liquid film enriched with Cu at the end of solidification.

Since the RAW-2024 alloy only differs from the ND-2024 alloy in the addition of CaB_6 , it can be concluded that these nanoparticles are responsible for grain refinement. CaB_6 nanoparticles within the α -Al grains and at the grain boundaries act differently in terms of grain

refinement. When examining the CaB_6 - α -Al interface using FFT, two highly coherent crystallographic ORs were determined for CaB_6 and α -Al. This coherence is favored by the minimal lattice parameter mismatch of only +2.55% between CaB_6 nanoparticles ($a = 4.145\text{\AA}$) and α -Al ($a = 4.049\text{\AA}$), and is an indication for the high effectiveness of CaB_6 nanoparticles as heterogeneous grain refiners. The necessary critical undercooling (ΔT_N) for heterogeneous nucleation reduced with decreasing lattice parameter mismatch between nucleant particle and matrix [48]. Not every CaB_6 nanoparticle acts as a nucleant: the majority accumulate in the liquid between the growing grains and are pushed to the grain boundaries [49] where they act as microstructure stabilizers, via Zener-pinning [12,38,50]. This grain stabilizing effect is essential to prevent grain growth during the LPBF process and any subsequent heat treatment.

The EDX chemical maps show that an Al-Cu-Mg containing phase is precipitated on the fine CaB_6 nanoparticles. Both Cu and Mg are supersaturated in the α -Al matrix as a result of the high cooling rate. Due to the layer-by-layer melting, areas of solidified material are exposed to heat again, causing the precipitation of forcibly dissolved elements. At the ceramic nanoparticle-matrix interface, an increased dislocation density is present, supporting the diffusion of dissolved elements to the CaB_6 nanoparticles. Furthermore, small spherical particles, consisting of Al, Mg and O are visible: such O containing particles are typical for LPBF aluminum since O is present on the particle surface in the form of a thin oxide layer.

In this work, the as-built ND-2024 material has a yield strength of 348 ± 16 MPa, an ultimate tensile strength of 391 ± 22 MPa and a total elongation to fracture of $12.6 \pm 0.6\%$. This high-strength and elongation are due to the fine-grained equiaxed microstructure, which increases the strength according to Hall-Petch [51] and precipitation hardening through the CaB_6 nanoparticles and the Al_2Cu phase. The full strength potential of this alloy can be achieved through the precipitation of complex hardening phases through subsequent T6 aging. The heat treatment, however, has to be specially adapted to the alloy processed with LPBF to avoid grain coarsening during the solution heat treatment. Further research is needed to study this more in detail.

5. Conclusion

This study analyses the ability and efficiency of CaB_6 as a heterogeneous grain refiner for LPBF Al alloys. Process behavior, microstructure, and the mechanical properties of a 2024 aluminum, modified with 2 wt% CaB_6 nanoparticles were systematically investigated and compared with a conventional 2024 alloy. The main conclusions can be summarized as follows:

1. The LPBF processability of the 2024 alloy modified with CaB_6 is considerably improved compared to the conventional 2024 alloy. Porosity and solidification cracking were almost entirely eliminated.
2. The addition of 2.0 wt% CaB_6 leads to a transition from a columnar to an equiaxed microstructure and significant grain refinement. The homogenous equiaxed microstructure, with a grain size of 0.91 ± 0.32 μm , provides a much higher resistance to solidification cracking compared to the columnar microstructure of the conventional 2024 alloy.

Fig. 10. The representative tensile stress-strain curve of the as-built ND-2024 material. Arrows indicate the serrated deformation behavior caused by the Portevin-Le Chatelier (PLC) effect.

- A coherent interface between the cube-shaped ceramic nanoparticles and the α -Al matrix demonstrates the high efficiency of CaB_6 as a heterogeneous grain refiner for aluminum.
- Most CaB_6 nanoparticles accumulate in the liquid between the growing grains and function as microstructure stabilizers at the grain boundaries, via Zener-Pinning.
- The tensile strength and elongation at fracture of the as-built 2024 alloy modified with 2.0 wt% CaB_6 is 391 ± 22 MPa and $12.6 \pm 0.6\%$, respectively.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Philipp Mair: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. **Valerie Sue Götting:** Investigation, Writing - review & editing. **Tobias Rainer:** Methodology. **Nikolaus Weinberger:** Investigation. **Ilse Letofsky-Papst:** Investigation. **Stefan Mitsche:** Investigation. **Gerhard Leichtfried:** Supervision, Writing - review & editing.

Data availability

The raw/processed data required to reproduce these findings cannot be shared at this time as the data also forms part of an ongoing study.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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